

**PSYCHOLOGY IN DENTISTRY: THE MOST IMPORTANT ASPECTS
OF CORRECT COMMUNICATION WITH THE PATIENT**

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Introduction. Interest in the topic "Psychology in dentistry" is predictable, since dentistry works not in the "doctor-to-patient organ" but in the "person-to-person" system. Since dentists do not always pay enough attention to the individual characteristics of the patient, there are at least three reasons why it is useful for dentists to fully acquire psychological knowledge of the possibilities determined by active communication with the patient. 1. The nature of the relationship between the dentist and the patient affects the effectiveness of treatment. 2. Friendly relationship between the doctor and the patient affects the creation and preservation of clients (practice), this is for doctors who practice privately and / or those working in commercial reception. 3. A positive attitude, a favorable psychological climate at work improves the quality of life of the doctor himself. We spend about 1/3 of our lives at work, and it is better to spend it in a good mood. method. The practical work of dentists is most successful when the doctor and the patient help each other, when it is based on a mutually beneficial relationship. It is desirable to acquire basic knowledge of the psychology of the patient so that psychological problems do not become a serious limitation of the professional practice of dentists. When building relationships with patients, at least their age characteristics should be taken into account. Also, the doctor should remember the need for an individual approach to the patient. Regardless of the characteristics of the dentist, it is necessary, first of all, to be able to competently build communication with adults (Table 1). In one

situation, adults are patients, in another, they are the parents of patients who are responsible for their health and monitor the implementation of medical recommendations by children, including adolescents. Unlike situations in which adult patients are treated, a special approach to the organization of the reception of children is required, since problems often arise with children during dental appointments that can interfere with the implementation of therapeutic measures. The basis of successful work in pediatric dentistry is based on the ability to control the behavior of children during appointments with medical staff. Tips on how to make this work ergonomic and not waste time on unproductive techniques are given in the table. 2. The aspect of the dentist's relationship with families with children in the clinic should be noted separately. Often communication is limited to solving the issue of the presence or absence of parents in the office and teaching parents to take care of the child's oral cavity, but parents, at the development stage, have a significant influence on the emotional state of the child, the approach to treatment, the personality of the doctor and characteristic psychological features. Early maturity (20-25 years old) When communicating with patients and parents of this age, it is not particularly difficult to convey new information. High indicators of mental functioning, flexibility and mobility in decision-making, most likely learning and persuasion. This should be emphasized, since the criterion of novelty itself makes them more perceptible. Average age (25-65 years old) First minute period: 25-40 years old. On the one hand, it is more difficult for an adult to acquire new ideas after the age of 25. Curiosity passes, mental connections are generally established, and the ability to assimilate is almost exhausted. There is a decline in non-verbal functions, which becomes noticeable by the age of 40. On the other hand, during adult development, the degree of learning increases individually. People of this age are very aware of new information, but it is best to state it based on other criteria, such as importance, the needs of the person himself, logical justification. New information must be integrated into the established system of

human concepts. Second minute period: 40-55 (60) years for women, 60 (65) years for men. Oral function reaches its highest level after 40-45 years. At the same time, there is a slight decrease in the plasticity of the nervous system, stereotyped thinking and behavior. It becomes more difficult to understand and adapt to new things, and most people do not notice the changes that occur in them. It is better to give the presence of something familiar with information, so that it is easier for the patient to adapt it to his categorical system, especially if it conflicts with his established ideas, but it is not always easy for those who are in demand and appreciate the acceptance of the new in society. Despite the general patterns of development, it must be remembered that a person has such qualities of personality. For example, an active creative personality of this age group is characterized by an easy recognition of new ideas and the rejection of previous ones, a wide range of interests, the ability to reassess values in the main areas of activity, flexibility, critical thinking. Therefore, the approach to such people must be appropriate. Patients over 65 years old (very often "unemployed grandparents") 1. One of the main features of this age group is the individualization of age-related changes. The speed of speech reactions slows down, sensitivity to different types of colors and sounds decreases, image memory weakens, mechanical impressions deteriorate. But in some cases, the preservation of indicators of speech reactions in the normal range for adolescents is observed, human consciousness and vocabulary continue to grow, semantic memory is preserved. It is advisable to speak slowly and clearly with patients of this group, paraphrase or simply repeat and correct the most important points. It is necessary to take time to formulate and consider the answer. Since older people show significant individual differences, an individual approach to the patient becomes more important. It is necessary to pay attention to non-verbal communication. Characteristics of the age group Presence of parents The main problem of reception (except for medicines) is what to do before 3 years. An unstable nervous system, sudden mood swings, lack of vocabulary for long-term

(more than 1 year) negative memories (up to 1-1.5 years old) is very limited. Benefits: oral care, gifts with age (dental slots, toys). An adult should be in the office, and if necessary, the child will sit on the hands of the parents. Children's behavior can be radically opposed: from a complete lack of fear (for the first time) to complete negativity (for the first time, or vice versa - long-standing negative experience) 1. 2. Open mouth Provide access to the oral cavity for more than 7-10 minutes. 3. Do not work in large quantities at once 4. 5. Negative thoughts about the crying of other children. Adverse reactions to parental dentist excitement and excitement: clothing (specifications. bright details such as suits, ears, mustaches like butterflies, hats, colored masks). To improve the quality and speed of work, we work with 4 manual assistants. Premedication (performed by an anesthesiologist!). Treatment under anesthesia after 3 visits (from one or various doctors) attempts to establish contact with the child's negative attitude. Provide parents with information on effective prevention to reduce the risk of relapse. Psychologist's advice: To get rid of fear and stress, it is necessary to focus on the emotional state of the parents. Distraction manipulations aimed at children (persuasion in this case will not be very useful and can waste time). Between 3-6 years old, the behavior of children in this age group can be considered cautious. For children aged 3-4 years, it is common for fear to appear, even if the previous treatment was painless and successful. At 5-6 years, the child usually responds clearly and is ready for treatment, or does not react at all. It is not necessary to have parents in the office, but this is undesirable, since children often behave badly in front of their mother and father. The placebo effect is very effective. For example, "brave water" or courage pills. You can use plain water or vitamin supplements as a placebo. 1. 2. Open mouth Provide access to the oral cavity for more than 10-15 minutes. 3. Do not work on large amounts at once 4. Negative reactions to the crying of other children, irritability of the parent. 5. Fatigue during treatment increased, especially later in the day (after kindergarten / development classes). Dental experience: With sedative syrups, tablets, herbs,

herbal general anesthesia, pre-medication is recommended for a wide range of work (treatment and removal). To give the opportunity to see the verification process, to show what the instruments are doing in the mouth. Step-by-step technique of local anesthesia (to distract from the injection). It is preferable to use non-traumatic methods. Toys and cartoons can be used as temporary distractions (to perform certain operations). Encourage limited vocabulary: always words, age-appropriate gifts (educational toys, stickers). Advice from psychologists: at 3-4 years old, it is much easier to persuade and condition the child for treatment (to win the child and ask for sympathy, attention, sympathy, play together), distraction (cartoons). At 5-6 years old, you can refuse and condition the treatment using the rights of favorite children's characters (cartoons, TV series, etc.).). For example, they will treat the teeth and teach how to do it. The role of games at the reception should also not be underestimated, since a comfortable life allows the child to relax and relax more, especially when you have to wait a little. It is still important to control the mood of the parents. At 7-10 years old, increased anxiety, many questions. Ability and awareness to tolerate the need for treatment. Age-appropriate gifts (educational games, books, comics, educational weapons). It is advisable to exclude the presence of parents in the office. The behavior of children of this age is as follows: "I'm an adult, but I'm a coward. "The reception time is 30-45 minutes, a maximum of 1 hour. Treatment should take place on a day when the child is not too busy with classes, clubs and departments. Increased fatigue and fatigue in the evening can negatively affect the general mood of the treatment, even if initially positive. Dentist's experience: premedication with herbal and herbal sedative syrups, tablets. To check the verification process, give the opportunity to show what the tool is doing in the mouth. The main activity of children of this age in the psychologist's counseling hall: reading cartoons, drawing, sometimes doing homework. Thus, attention is paid to an atmosphere of comfort and tranquility. Explain to children how to avoid such problems in the future. What other treatments are

there? Characteristics of the age group Presence of parents The main problems at the reception (in addition to medical problems) What to do Instability of mood in 11-year-olds, negative, bravo, sometimes "adult" behavior, often adolescent behavior is too closed (fear) or too emotional (bravo). Age-appropriate gifts (teen magazines, movies), which should exclude the presence of parents in the office. Patience, courtesy and composure on the part of the doctor are key to success for patients at this age. The behavior of children at this age is the most difficult and unpredictable, making him think "I know everything and I don't want anything.". Dentist's experience: talk about the treatment, explain the nature of the operation. For them, it is necessary to find out the topics that interest the teenager and become possessive enough to talk to him as an adult. In communication with teenagers, the psychologist's advice should be to talk about the need for pressure and non-pressure treatment, focusing on the importance of dentistry not only for health, but also for external beauty and success (a beautiful smile is the key). How the treatment attitude of parents affects the emotional mood of the child until adolescence. During the treatment of a child, the doctor communicates with the child and adults, you must be a good child psychologist and establish psychological contact with the parents. The dentist should take into account all the above aspects and actively install the adult so that the child can express positive emotions.

Conclusion: In communication between doctors and adult patients / parents of patients, persuasion is the most widely used method of influence, the most ethical. Persuasive logic is open to perception, trusting facts known by a trusted person, the information should be clear, logical and cause an emotional reaction. Yet, despite the existence of patterns, age-related characteristics do not appear in a "pure form" and are not absolute and immutable characteristics. Since people have qualities like personality, only a creative and attentive attitude towards the patient can bring tangible benefits.

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